

Documentation of search strategies University Library search consultation group

Date: October 2019

Topic/research question: What is known from the existing literature about user-driven innovations for self-care, co-care and health care?

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Librarian(s): Magdalena Svanberg & Emma-Lotta Säätelä

Databases:

1. Medline (Ovid)
 2. Web of Science Core Collection
 3. PsycInfo (Ovid)
 4. Cinahl (Ebsco)
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Total number of hits:

- Before deduplication: 8,082
 - After deduplication: 6,273
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Comments:

PRISMA 2009 Flow Diagram¹

¹ From: Moher D, Liberati A, Tetzlaff J, Altman DG, The PRISMA Group (2009). Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses: The PRISMA Statement. PLoS Med 6(6): e1000097. doi:10.1371/journal.pmed1000097. For more information, visit www.prisma-statement.org.

1. Medline

Interface: Ovid MEDLINE(R) and Epub Ahead of Print, In-Process & Other Non-Indexed Citations and Daily

Date of Search: 15 October 2019

Number of hits: 3,443

Comment: In Ovid, two or more words are automatically searched as phrases; i.e. no quotation marks are needed

Field labels

- exp/ = exploded MeSH term
- / = non exploded MeSH term
- .ti,ab,kf. = title, abstract and author keywords
- adjx = within x words, regardless of order
- * = truncation of word for alternate endings

#	Searches	Results
1	((adult child* or patient* or care giver* or caregiver* or carer* or family or husband* or "next of kin*" or partner* or spouse* or user or wife or wives) adj1 (directed or driven or driving or initiated)).ti,ab,kf.	4150
2	(co creat* or co design* or collaborative creation* or collaborativ* created or "do it yourself" or "doing it for themselves" or diy or e patient* or lead patient* or participatory design* or public driven or superuser*).ti,ab,kf.	3444
3	Patient participation/	24568
4	or/1-3	31910
5	Equipment design/	144620
6	Inventions/	1720
7	Organizational innovation/	23978
8	Diffusion of Innovation/	17239
9	(innovat* or invention* or invented).ti,ab,kf.	128952
10	Self-Management/	1492
11	exp Self-Help Devices/	11126
12	exp Self care/	52825
13	(assistive technolog* or co care or self care or self help device* or self management* or self monitor* or self track*).ti,ab,kf.	42096
14	or/5-13	388764
15	4 and 14	3235
16	(co innovat* or patient* innovat* or patient design*).ti,ab,kf.	219
17	15 or 16	3443

2. Web of Science Core Collection

Interface: Clarivate Analytics		Field labels
Date of Search: 15 October 2019		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TS/Topic = title, abstract, author keywords and Keywords Plus • NEAR/x = within x words, regardless of order • * = truncation of word for alternate endings
Number of hits: 1,486		Note: sometimes "quotation marks" are needed for single search terms to avoid automatic term mapping (lemmatization).
# 11	1,486	#10 AND #9
# 10	11,179,378	TS=(disabilit* or disorder* or disease* or health* or medical* or medicine* or patient* or psychiatr*)
# 9	4,684	#8 OR #7
# 8	428	TS=("co innovat*" or "patient* innovat*" or "patient design*")
# 7	4,301	#6 AND #3
# 6	554,001	#5 OR #4
# 5	56,965	TOPIC: (("assistive technolog*" or "co care" or "self care" or "self help device*" or "self management*" or "self monitor*" or "self track*"))
# 4	498,702	TOPIC: ((innovat* or invention* or invented))
# 3	42,438	#2 OR #1
# 2	20,170	TS=("co creat*" or "co design*" or "collaborative creation*" or "collaborativ* created" or "do it yourself" or "doing it for themselves" or diy or "e patient*" or "lead patient*" or "participatory design*" or "public driven" or superuser*)
# 1	22,369	TOPIC: (((("adult child*" or patient* or "care giver*" or caregiver* or carer* or family or husband* or "next of kin*" or partner* or spouse* or user or wife or wives) NEAR/1 (directed or driven or driving or initiated))))

3. Psycinfo

<p>Interface: Ovid</p> <p>Date of Search: 15 October 2019</p> <p>Number of hits: 760</p> <p>Comment: In Ovid, two or more words are automatically searched as phrases; i.e. no quotation marks are needed</p>		<p>Field labels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • exp/ = exploded controlled term • / = non exploded controlled term • .ti,ab,id. = title, abstract and author keywords • adjx = within x words, regardless of order • * = truncation of word for alternate endings
#	Searches	Results
1	exp client participation/	2032
2	((adult child* or patient* or care giver* or caregiver* or carer* or family or husband* or "next of kin*" or partner* or spouse* or user or wife or wives) adj1 (directed or driven or driving or initiated)).ti,ab,id.	1154
3	(co creat* or co design* or collaborative creation* or collaborativ* created or "do it yourself" or "doing it for themselves" or diy or e patient* or lead patient* or participatory design* or public driven or superuser*).ti,ab,id.	3267
4	or/1-3	6414
5	innovation/	12769
6	exp product design/	5606
7	(innovat* or invention* or invented).ti,ab,id.	62414
8	or/5-7	67742
9	exp self-management/	6385
10	self-monitoring/	2883
11	exp assistive technology/	9925
12	(assistive technolog* or co care or self care or self help device* or self management* or self monitor* or self track*).ti,ab,id.	24688
13	or/5-12	103132
14	4 and 13	683
15	(co innovat* or patien*t innovat* or patient design*).ti,ab,id.	82
16	14 or 15	760

4. Cinahl

#	Searches	Results
S14	S12 OR S13	2,391
S13	TI ("co innovat*" or "patient* innovat*" or "patient design*") OR AB ("co innovat*" or "patient* innovat*" or "patient design*")	144
S12	S4 AND S11	2,255
S11	S5 OR S6 OR S7 OR S8 OR S9 OR S10	184,189
S10	TI ("assistive technolog*" or "co care" or "self care" or "self help device*" or "self management*" or "self monitor*" or "self track*") OR AB ("assistive technolog*" or "co care" or "self care" or "self help device*" or "self management*" or "self monitor*" or "self track*")	29,539
S9	(MH "Assistive Technology Devices+")	31,412
S8	(MH "Self Care+")	44,835
S7	TI (innovat* or invention* or invented) OR AB (innovat* or invention* or invented)	49,209
S6	(MH "Diffusion of Innovation+")	12,735
S5	(MH "Equipment Design+")	43,859
S4	S1 OR S2 OR S3	23,406
S3	(MH "Consumer Participation")	17,926
S2	TI ("co design*" or "co creat*" or "collaborative creation*" or "collaborativ* created" or "do it yourself" or "doing it for themselves" or diy or "e patient*" or "lead patient*" or "participatory design*" or "public driven" or superuser*) OR AB ("co design*" or "co creat*" or "collaborative creation*" or "collaborativ* created" or "do it yourself" or "doing it for themselves" or diy or "e patient*" or "lead patient*" or "participatory design*" or "public driven" or superuser*)	2,321
S1	TI (("adult child*" or patient* or "care giver*" or caregiver* or carer* or family or husband* or "next of kin*" or partner* or spouse* or user or wife or wives) N1	3,379

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(directed or driven or driving or initiated)) OR AB (("adult child*" or patient* or "care giver*" or caregiver* or carer* or family or husband* or "next of kin*" or partner* or spouse* or user or wife or wives) N1 (directed or driven or driving or initiated))	
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